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List of Acronyms

AMS	Alpha Magnet Spectrometer
BGO	Bismuth germanium oxide
COSTEP	Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer
DOY	Day of year
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
ESA	European Space Agency
FFS	Force field solution
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Rays
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
HET	High Energy Telescope
HMI	Hahn Meitner Institute
MIP	Minimum Ionizing Particle
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NM	Neutron Monitor
PAMELA	Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SSD	Solid State Detector

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Calibration of energetic particle instruments is a multistep process involving preflight testing, in-flight adjustments, and continuous monitoring. It combines experimental data with theoretical modeling to achieve accurate measurements, essential for advancing our understanding of space radiation, cosmic rays, and fundamental particle interactions.

The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) is part of the Comprehensive Suprathermal and Energetic Particle Analyzer (COSTEP) suite onboard SOHO and was designed to measure the flux of proton and helium isotopes in the energy range from 4 to 50 MeV/amu. It was Kühl et al. (2015) who adapted the $\frac{dE}{dx} - \frac{dE}{dx}$ -method (see section 2.2) to EPHIN, extending the energy range for protons to above 1 GeV. However, in 2017 due to the aging of the instrument, the method needed to be adapted. In this deliverable, the modified $\frac{dE}{dx} - \frac{dE}{dx}$ -method is described in section 3.1 and compared successfully to the one by Kühl et al. (2015).

As described in deliverable 3.1 the EPHIN model was improved utilizing an improved spacecraft model of SOHO. In Section 3.1.1 the results of the GEometry ANd Tracking (GEANT)-4 computation are summarized and results for two FFSs that describe the GCR spectra in November 2009 and June 2001 are compared to the EPHIN measurements. Taking into account the uncertainties, we find that our model computations agree within about 30% with the actual measurements.

In section 3.1.2 we applied the bowtie method to selected sub-data sets in order to derive the helium and proton fluxes in certain energy ranges. The results are compared to quiet time Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics (PAMELA) helium spectra and AMS-02 proton spectra.

From the above comparisons, we found that the EPHIN derived proton and helium fluxes agree with the ones obtained from the spectrometers with an accuracy of less than 30%.

1 Introduction

Calibrating energetic particle instruments like the [EPHIN](#) aboard [SOHO](#) is a crucial process to ensure the accuracy and reliability of measurements in space missions and particle physics experiments. [EPHIN](#) measures particles, viz. protons, electrons, and helium over a wide range of energies from MeV to several hundred of MeV. The calibration process establishes the relationship between the instrument's raw data (e.g., counts) and the physical properties of the detected particles (e.g., energy, flux, charge, and mass).

Space Environment: Instruments deployed in space encounter varying radiation environments, changing particle flux, and anisotropy, complicating calibration efforts.

Aging Effects: Detectors may degrade over time as a result of radiation damage or changes in electronics, requiring ongoing recalibration. [SOHO](#) and Chandra [EPHIN](#) underwent several reconfiguration in 1997 and 2017 due to two detectors becoming noisy (see for example [Kühl & Heber 2019](#), and references therein).

Energy Range and Resolution: [SOHO EPHIN](#) was designed to cover the energy range from 4 MeV/amu to above 50 MeV/amu for hydrogen and helium and 0.15 MeV to above 10 MeV for electrons ([Müller-Mellin et al. 1995](#)) using the $\frac{dE}{dx} - E$ -method. [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#), [Kühl et al. \(2016\)](#) and [Kühl et al. \(2017\)](#) showed that the energy range could be extended using the $\frac{dE}{dx} - \frac{dE}{dx}$ -method.

Key Steps in the Calibration of Energetic Particle Instruments

1. Characterization of Detector Response

Pre-flight Characterization: Before launch the detector response is characterized using well-known particle sources in controlled environments. Single Solid State Detector ([SSD](#)) of the [EPHIN](#) were irradiated with radioactive isotopes. The full telescope was calibrated with different ions from hydrogen to Lithium at the Hahn Meitner Institute ([HMI](#)) in Berlin and with electrons at the accelerator in Gent (for details see [Sierks 1997](#)).

Efficiency calibration: This involves determining the probability that the instrument detects an incident particle of a given type and energy. It often requires detailed modeling of the detector geometry and material interactions using software like [GEANT4](#) ([Agostinelli et al. 2003](#)).

Geometric Factor Calculation: The geometric factor quantifies the effective area of the detector through which the particles are counted. This parameter depends on the instrument design, including the field of view and the acceptance angle ([Sullivan 1971](#)).

2. On-orbit Calibration and Monitoring

In-flight Calibration: After launch, calibration needs to be periodically checked using e.g. the energy loss of Minimum Ionizing Particles ([MIPs](#)).

Cross-calibration: Instruments may also be cross-calibrated against other well-characterized instruments operating on the same mission or nearby platforms. Here we utilize published data from [AMS-02](#) ([Aguilar et al. 2021](#)) and [PAMELA](#) ([Adriani et al. 2016b](#)).

3. Background and Noise Characterization

Noise Reduction: Understanding the noise characteristics (thermal noise, electronic noise) of the instrument is essential for accurately interpreting low-energy loss particle events.

Background Radiation: Instruments are exposed to cosmic rays and other high-energy particles, contributing to the background signal. Calibration procedures include background subtraction or mitigation strategies.

4. Data Analysis and Calibration Correction

Spectral Unfolding: For instruments that measure an integrated response over an energy range, unfolding techniques are applied to derive the true energy spectrum of the particles from the measured data.

Dead-Time Correction: The finite processing time of the detector can lead to missed events, especially in high-flux environments. Calibration must account for this dead time effect.

2 Previous work

2.1 Description of the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN)

The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)/European Space Agency (ESA) SOHO was launched in 1995 and is since 1996 orbiting the Lagrangian point L1. The scientific payload of the spacecraft consists of several remote and in-situ instruments. The Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN, Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) is part of the COSTEP suite onboard SOHO. A schematic view of

Figure 1: Sketch of the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (taken from Kühl et al. 2015)

the EPHIN instrument is shown in Fig. 1. The instrument consists of a stack of six SSDs (labeled A-F in Fig. 1) that is surrounded by a scintillation detector (G), which acts as an anticoincidence. Stopping ions are identified by applying the $\frac{dE}{dx} - E$ -method. Since the data rate is limited, energy losses in detectors A-E can only be transmitted for a statistical ensemble of all particles counted by EPHIN. A crude separation between electrons, protons, and helium has been introduced for different penetration depths,

that is, different coincidences by introducing different energy-loss thresholds in **SSD A** (for details see Müller-Mellin et al. 1995).

In order to monitor time-dependent instrumental issues, among others, the count rates of each detector of **EPHIN** are recorded independently of any coincidence condition. These single detector count rates for all detectors are shown in Figure 2 together with the temperature of the **EPHIN** electronic box.

Figure 2: Temperature and count rates of the single detectors of **SOHO/EPHIN**.

Although sudden increases in all detectors can be related to **SEP** events and the 11-year variations seen in the count rates of detectors B, F and G correspond to the **GCR** modulation, other signatures give insights on the technical condition of the different detectors. The anticoincidence scintillator (G) as well as **SSD B** and F show no change in behavior during the course of the mission, the count rate of **SSD A**, the first detector at the very top of the stack, clearly shows a correlation with the annual temperature variations of the instrument from around 2003. The count rates of the **SSDs E** and D have increased by orders of magnitude due to detector noise around 1997 and 2013, respectively. To account for these issues, the **EPHIN** instrument was switched to failure modes on October 31, 1996 and October 4, 2017,

respectively. The failure modes prevent dead-time issues due to the electronic noise but are reducing the energy resolution, i.e. the nominal four proton channels are merged into three and two channels, respectively. The count rate of the SSD C is increasing more gradually in the last decades, but is still below critical conditions.

2.2 Extension of SOHO EPHIN to energies up to several 100 MeV

Kühl et al. (2015) utilized the $(\Delta E - \Delta E)$ method technique to identify the energy range for hydrogen, helium and electrons that passes the EPHIN detector stack. It involves measuring the energy loss ΔE of a particles in SSD C and D:

Principle of the $(\Delta E - \Delta E)$ method When a charged particle passes through a material, it loses energy due to interactions with the electrons and nuclei of the material (ionization and excitation). The amount of energy lost per unit thickness $(\frac{dE}{dx})$ depends on the charge, energy, and mass of the particle, as well as the properties of the material:

The energy loss $(\frac{dE}{dx})$ is described by the **Bethe-Bloch equation**, which depends on the charge (z), mass (m), and velocity (v):

$$\frac{dE}{dx} \propto \frac{z^2}{\beta^2} \ln \left(\frac{const}{\beta^2(1 - \beta^2)} \right),$$

where $\beta = v/c$.

The particle passes through two detectors in sequence: a **thin SSD** (where the energy loss is proportional to $\frac{dE}{dx}$) and a **thicker detector** (to measure more of the remaining energy). The HET aboard Solar Orbiter (SolO) utilizes a second thin detector that allows determining the input direction of the particle (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020). The traditional way is to plot the two ΔE measurements against each other (ΔE_1 vs. ΔE_2) to form a $\Delta E - \Delta E$ map. Particles with the same charge and mass form distinct loci on this map due to the specific way their energy loss changes with energy (see for example Terasa et al. 2013, and references therein).

Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. (2020) improved the method by implementing two thin SSDs on each side of the BGO-calorimeter (see the left panel of Fig. 3. This is then used to minimize the width of the energy loss distribution on each side taking $\min(\Delta E_{A_i}, \Delta E_{B_i})$ for $i = 1, 2$ (see for example Kühl et al. 2015, and references therein). When computing the ratio of the energy loss minima left and right of the

Figure 3: Left panel: Cross-section of one of the HET unit (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. (2020)). The right panel displays the ratio of the $\min(\Delta E_{A_i}, \Delta E_{B_i})$ for $i = 1$ and $i = 2$ as function of the seen energy in the BGO scintillator (detector C). From left to right the tracks of hydrogen, helium and heavier ions can be identified. The introduction of "two" SSDs on both sides of the BGO-calorimeter allows to differentiate between particles moving from left to right (y -values below 1) and from right to the left (y -values above 1).

BGO calorimeter, the minimized energy loss is for an extended energy range lower in the detector pair

that is hit first by the particle (see the right panel of Fig. 3). Thus in this specific energy range one is able to differentiate between particles entering the instrument from the left or the right. In summary:

Advantages:

- Allows for precise particle identification across a wide range of energies.
- Can differentiate particles even if they have the same energy but different mass and charge.

Challenges:

- Requires precise calibration of the detectors to account for material thickness and other effects.
- Limited by particle energy ranges that detectors can accurately measure without saturation or inefficiencies.

Table 1: Specification of the SSDs in EPHIN (for details see Sierks 1997)

Detector	A	B	C	D	E
type	Ion-implanted	Ion-implanted	Lithium-drifted	Lithium-drifted	Ion-implanted
Thickness [μm]	150 ± 10	300 ± 15	3000 ± 10	5000 ± 10	700 ± 15
Active area [mm]	1130	1130	1500	1500	5000
Number of segments	6	6	1	1	1
Deadlayer front [μm]	1.3	1.3	0.5	0.5	0.8
Deadlayer back [μm]	0.8	0.8	40	40	0.8
Capacity [pF]	140^1	70^1	55	30	850
Leackage current 20 °C [nA]	0.1	0.1	10	10	0.5
HV [V]	-30	-60	-J-400	+600	-140
A-res. [keV] FWHM	36	36	< 1ii0	< 150	80
B-res. [keV] FWHM	12	12	n.a.	n.a.	70

¹ per segment

Application to the Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN) Sierks (1997) applied the $\frac{dE}{dx}$ – $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -method utilizing the SSDs A to E summarized in Tab. 1. Although SSD E has a thickness of $s = 5000\mu\text{m}$ it has been chosen because it is the last energy loss analyzed SSD in the EPHIN stack allowing to focus on forward penetrating particles. The energy loss is then compared to the total energy loss in the SSDs A to E corresponding to a thickness of $d=13450\mu\text{m}$. The result for the period from January 7 to January 12, 1996 is shown in Fig. 4. Marked in the figure are regions, e.g. 'A' to 'C' in the inlet for which the entries are caused by Helium. A', 'B' and 'C' mark the three energy channels corresponding to energies between 53 and 126 MeV/amu (Sierks 1997). Due to the loss of SSD E the method could not be applied further. Note the energy loss in SSD F is not provided, so the capability to separate forward and backward penetrating helium and protons is further reduced. Kühl et al. (2015) have presented a method in order to extend the energy range of EPHIN for protons up to energies of above 1 GeV based on the energy loss data from SSDs A to D. Utilizing extensive GEANT4 simulations (Agostinelli et al.

Figure 4: Energy loss matrix of penetrating particles during the time period from January 7, 1996 to January 12, 1996. The energy loss in SSD E is shown over the seen energy loss in SSDs A to E. The inset displays the corresponding matrix for Helium only. 'A', 'B' and 'C' mark the three energy channels corresponding to energies between 53 and 126 MeV/amu (Sierks 1997).

2003) of the instrument (see also Köberle et al. 2024, hereafter D2.1), it has been shown that the initial energy of a given proton penetrating EPHIN (i.e. triggering detectors A to F) can be derived from the energy losses in SSD C and D. In contrast to the analysis of Sierks (1997), a separation of forward and backward penetrating protons is not possible, so the contribution of backward penetrating particles must be calculated (see also D2.1). Fig. 5 displays the current GEANT4 model based on the GDML description of the instrument (for details see D2.1). Due to too high noise in detector D (which ultimately leads to the switch on of EPHIN failure mode D), the method is restricted to data before 2017. However, those high energy measurements of GCRs (Kühl et al. 2016) as well as SEPs (Kühl et al. 2017) have been validated against measurements of GCRs and during the GLE71 in May 2012, as shown in Fig. 6 in the left and right panel, respectively. For details, see the above-mentioned publications.

With SSD D becoming noisy in 2017, the method of Kühl et al. (2015) could not be applied directly. Therefore, the method was adapted within SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) utilizing the energy loss in SSD B and C. As explained by Kühl et al. (2016), the energy resolution of the method relies on the energy loss resolution in the SSDs involved. Thus, utilizing in total 3300 μm instead of 8000 μm silicon we expect a severe reduction of the energy resolution (see Tab. 1). Fig. 7 shows on the left side in the upper and lower panels the energy loss per mm distribution of the SSDs B (black), C (red), and D (green) during May 2012 and May 2024 GLEs, respectively. Although all three distributions agree well with each other in 2012 the distribution in SSD D is very different from the other ones in 2017. As a consequence, energy losses per mm $\frac{dE}{dx} < 1.5 \text{ MeV/mm}$ are strongly influenced by the noise in SSD D. The right panel displays for each entry the minimum energy loss per

Figure 5: Left: a detailed view on the EPHIN GDML sensor model only. Right: EPHIN GDML model including a simplified spacecraft model of the SOHO spacecraft.

Figure 6: Left and right: Comparison of EPHIN GCR and SEP energy with different instruments (for details see Kühl et al. 2015, 2016, and references therein)

mm utilizing SSDs C and D (black) and SSDs C and B (red) for both periods, respectively. The upper panel shows that both distributions agree quite well with each other in 2012 for energy losses per mm $\frac{dE}{dx} > 0.55$ MeV/mm but differ significantly below that threshold. Note, the noise in SSD D does allow for

Figure 7: The upper and lower panel display the measurements on May 17, 2012 (GLE71) and May 11, 2024 (GLE74), respectively.

an energy determination for energy losses per mm above $\frac{dE}{dx} \geq 1.0$ MeV/mm. Therefore we will discuss the determination of the penetrating proton and helium fluxes separately.

3 EPHIN penetrating proton and helium spectra after September 2017

This section describes the method applied to compute helium and proton spectra utilizing the ansatz by Terasa et al. (2013) and Kühl et al. (2016), respectively.

3.1 Previous work on proton spectra

As can be seen in the right panels of Fig. 7 the energy loss distribution utilizes the minimum of the energy loss per mm in SSDs C and D together with the ones obtained using SSDs B and C for periods before 2017 agree quite well with each other. To estimate the effect of replacing SSD D with SSD B

we compute the energy spectra published by [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) for [GLE72](#) and for the January 6, 2014 [SEP](#) event using both distributions. We computed the energy spectra by modifying the program used by [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) to use the min(B,C) instead of the min(D,C) distribution with the same selection criteria. Fig. 8 shows the proton energy flux spectra ($\Phi|_{D,C}$, red symbols) and ($\Phi|_{B,C}$, black symbols) and the differences $(\Phi|_{B,C} - \Phi|_{D,C})/\Phi|_{D,C}$ in the left and right panels, respectively. The upper and lower panels give the proton flux spectra for the [GLE72](#) and for the January 6, 2014 event, respectively. In contrast to the energy spectra shown in [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) a lower energy resolution was chosen as discussed above. In the energy range from 50 MeV to about 500 MeV both derived energy spectra show differences that are smaller than 30% that is in the same magnitude of the systematic uncertainty of the method (for details see [Kühl et al. 2016](#), and references therein).

Thus we conclude that substituting the minimum energy loss per mm distribution derived by the SSDs D and C with the one derived by the one obtained utilizing the SSDs B and C lead to energy spectra that agree with each other within an accuracy of 30% in the range from 50 MeV to 500 MeV.

Figure 8: Proton energy flux spectra ($\Phi|_{D,C}$, red symbols) and ($\Phi|_{B,C}$, black symbols) and the differences $(\Phi|_{B,C} - \Phi|_{D,C})/\Phi|_{D,C}$ are shown in the left and right panels, respectively. The upper and lower panel give the results utilizing 10 bins for the [GLE72](#) and for the January 6, 2014 sub-[GLE](#) event, respectively (for details see text).

As discussed in detail in [Kühl et al. \(2016\)](#) for large SEP events forward penetrating protons dominate the energy loss distribution in the above-mentioned energy loss regime. The situation becomes more complex when investigating the variation of GCRs. Here, both protons and helium that penetrate the instrument from both sides may contribute. In what follows, we describe an extension of the method introduced by [Kühl et al. \(2016\)](#) and compare the results with the daily averaged AMS-02 GCR fluxes in the rigidity ranges from 1 GV to 1.7 GV published by [Aguilar et al. \(2021\)](#) from 2011 to the end of 2019 at solar minimum.

3.1.1 Energy response functions of EPHIN to penetrating protons and helium (forward modeling)

Following Kühl et al. (2016) we compute the energy loss distributions for protons, helium and electrons in the energy range from above 50 MeV/amu to 100 GeV/amu and for electrons in the energy range from a few MeV to 1 GeV for particles penetrating the sensor using the GDML model of EPHIN given in deliverable D.2 and an isotropic angular distribution (for computation principle of the response function see Sullivan 1971, and references to this paper). From the results of these computations we determine:

$$\frac{dE}{dx} = \min \left(\left. \frac{\Delta E}{3} \right|_C, \left. \frac{\Delta E}{5} \right|_D \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dE}{dx} = \min \left(\left. \frac{\Delta E}{3} \right|_C, \left. \frac{\Delta E}{0.265} \right|_B \right) \quad (2)$$

The corresponding response factor as function $F(E, \alpha)$ for particles of type α with incoming energy E in intervals of $\frac{dE}{dx}$ is shown in the left and right panel of Fig. 9 for the combination of detectors C and D and C and B, respectively. From top to bottom, the distributions for electrons, protons, and helium are shown. From the figure it is evident that all three types of particles can contribute to several $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -bins.

The functions displayed in Fig. 9 can be utilized to determine a $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -distribution for given input spectra $J_\alpha(E)$ by computing:

$$C \left(\frac{dE}{dx} \right) (t) = \int_{E=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\alpha=e,p,he} F_{\Delta E}(E, \alpha) J_\alpha(E, t) dE . \quad (3)$$

where $F_{\Delta E}(E, \alpha)$ is EPHIN's energy response function (for an energy loss rate $\frac{dE}{dx}$ computed from the energy losses ΔE in its B and C detectors) and $J_\alpha(E, t)$ are the a-priori unknown energy spectra for each particle type of interest. Often the GCR energy spectra $J_\alpha(E, t)$ are approximated by the so-called FFS with the modulation potential ϕ as a single parameter (see for example the upper panel of Fig. 10 and the discussion in Herbst et al. 2010, 2017, and references therein).

As an example, we chose quiet time periods in July 2001 and November 2009. 27-day AMS-02 quiet time data from Aguilar et al. (2018) have been approximated by the FFS published by Usoskin et al. (2005) for different time intervals for protons and helium to obtain the force field potential. The upper panel of Fig. 10 displays as an example AMS-02 energy spectra that correspond to force field potentials of $\Phi = 363$, $\Phi = 436$, $\Phi = 652$ and $\Phi = 660$ MV (taken from Caprotti et al. 2021). Such spectra are used as input for computing $C(\frac{dE}{dx})$ for June 2001 (solar minimum, $\Phi = 390$ MV) and November 2009 (solar maximum, $\Phi = 769$ MV), respectively. The orange histograms in the middle two panels show the result of the computation of $C(\frac{dE}{dx})$. The blue histograms show the ones obtained by EPHIN during the same period. The lower panel shows the differences between them. Although both distributions agree within 20% with each other in the $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -range between 0.5 MeV/mm to about 1.1 MeV/mm and above 1.5 MeV/mm, large discrepancies are found below 0.5 MeV/mm and in the range of about 1.1 to 1.5 MeV/mm. The first region can be explained by the residual detector noise that leads to a substantial broadening at low $\frac{dE}{dx}$ values. The second part might be explained by the fact that we neglect the contribution of ${}^3\text{He}$ in the simulation. At energies greater than a few hundred MeV/amu the ratio $\frac{{}^3\text{He}}{{}^4\text{He}}$ can be as high as 20% (see for example Aguilar et al. 2024, and references therein). When discussing the differences of 20% between the model results, it is important to note that the force field potential given by Usoskin et al. (2005) is computed from Neutron Monitor (NM) measurements. However, it has been shown that a FFS with a modulation potential derived by NMs may overestimate the flux at lower energies (Gieseler et al. 2017).

In summary we conclude that forward modeling of given GCR proton and helium spectra is capable to account for EPHIN measurements within the accuracy of less than 30% during quiet time periods.

Figure 9: From top to bottom the minimum of $\frac{dE}{dx}$ in SSD C and D (left column) and B and C (right column) as function of incoming energy for electrons (top panel), protons (middle panel) and helium (lower panel), respectively. For discussion see text.

Figure 10: The left and right panel display the simulated $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -distribution utilizing a FFS with a modulation potential of $\phi = 390$ MV (November 2009) and $\phi = 769$ MV (June 2001), respectively. For details see text.

3.1.2 Inversion of the $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -distribution

In the following section we will investigate the “inversion” of the “matrix” displayed in Fig. 9 to derive the incoming energy and energy spectra for protons and helium with energies above 100 MeV/amu. Thus, the observed $\frac{dE}{dx}$ -distribution is investigated in more detail by separating the different particles, here protons, helium, and electrons.

For this purpose, we computed $C(\frac{dE}{dx})$ for power-law spectra with spectral index $\gamma = -1$ and a helium to proton ratio of 0.1. The scaling of electrons to protons is arbitrarily chosen because of the very different energy ranges and electron-to-proton ratios during SEP-events (see for example [Dresing et al. 2024](#), and references therein). Fig. 11 shows the results for electrons (green), protons (blue), and helium (orange) separately. At $\frac{dE}{dx}$ above 1.13 MeV/mm (see also [Vainio et al. \(2024\)](#); Deliverable 5.1) the corresponding distribution of below 100 MeV protons and above a few hundred MeV/amu helium becomes ambiguous until the energy loss per mm exceeds about 2.5 MeV/mm when helium becomes the dominant element. At low $\frac{dE}{dx}$, protons and electrons compete with each other. During quiet times the contribution of electrons is less than a few percent ([Aguilar et al. 2023](#)).

Figure 11: Contribution of electrons (green histogram), protons (blue histogram) and helium (orange histogram) to the $C(\frac{dE}{dx})$ -distribution.

3.2 Helium spectra, comparison to PAMELA measurements

To effectively determine the response of EPHIN to high energy helium, a GEANT4 simulation was performed. To separate forward penetrating particles from backward penetrating particles, the difference in energy loss per detector depth in detectors can be used:

$$\lambda = \frac{\Delta E_{A-C}}{\Delta x} - \frac{\Delta E_D}{\Delta x}, \quad (4)$$

where ΔE_{A-C} denotes the energy loss in detectors A to C and Δx denotes the total thickness of these detectors. As a particle loses energy while penetrating a detector, particles should lose more energy per depth in the detectors they pass first, leading to $\lambda > 0$ for backwards particles, while $\lambda < 0$ for forward

Figure 12: The left panel displays λ over the energy loss in the 4 detectors A-D (seen energy). Particles with $\lambda < 0$ should have come from the nominal viewing direction, particles with $\lambda > 0$ should have come from the back. The red boxes are used to calculate response functions. As an example the right panel displays the response function for the box marked by the red arrow, corresponding to energies seen between $\Delta E = 35$ MeV and $\Delta E = 40$ MeV. Note the acceptance to backwards penetrating particles (orange histogram). This influence increases with rising overall particle energy (and lower energy loss in detectors A-D). The red line denotes the primary energy range of the box.

Figure 13: Resulting Helium spectra for the second half of 2006 (excluding December). PAMELA results from [Adriani et al. \(2016a\)](#) are shown for comparison.

particles. This is depicted in the left panel of Fig. 12. The red rectangles show specific boxes chosen to represent different energy ranges.

As an example the right panel of Fig. 12 displays the response function for the box marked by the red arrow corresponding to energies seen between $\Delta E = 35$ MeV and $\Delta E = 40$ MeV. Note the acceptance to backwards penetrating particles for this box given by the orange histogram. Fig. 13 shows as the helium energy spectra obtained from Day of year (DOY) 200 to 302, 2006 in comparison with measurements from the PAMELA instrument. From the figure it becomes evident that the helium fluxes obtained by EPHIN are within the limited statistics in good agreement with the one from PAMELA.

Extending the method described in [Terasa et al. \(2013\)](#) and [Kühl et al. \(2015\)](#) to higher energy losses utilizing the direction information from **SSD D leads to helium energy spectra up to 250 MeV/amu that are in good agreement with the ones obtained by PAMELA.**

Table 2: Upper table: AMS-02 channels used in our analysis. Lower table: Energy ranges utilized for the comparison with AMS-02 from EPHIN

AMS Energy channel/GV	E_l /MeV	E_u /MeV		
1	433	554		
1.4	554	690		
ΔE_l /(MeV/mm)	ΔE_u /(MeV/mm)	E_{eff} /MeV	R/(cm ² sr)	Segment
0.45	0.52	679.	64.4	$A = B = 0$
0.52	0.64	505.	56.1	$A = B = 0$
0.45	0.52	743.	1626.3	all
0.52	0.64	539.	1293.5	all
0.45	0.52	699.	404.1	$A_i = B_i$
0.52	0.64	523.	337.0	$A_i = B_i$
0.45	0.52	735.	410.8	$B = 0$
0.52	0.64	529.	323.9	$B = 0$

3.3 Comparison of EPHIN to AMS-02 fluxes

Daily averaged proton fluxes from the AMS-02 instrument have been published by Aguilar et al. (2021). AMS-02 provides the flux of protons in different rigidity bins that can be converted to energy bins. Due to the limitations discussed above, only two of the AMS channels can be used for a direct comparison with EPHIN within the energy range from 433 to 690 MeV given in Tab. 2. The corresponding energy channels from EPHIN for different segment combinations (for definition see Sierks 1997) are summarized below for several segment combinations. Note that we optimized our choice for the segment combination $A = 0$ and $B = 0$. The corresponding response functions are displayed in the left panels of Fig. 14 for the upper and lower cut in $\frac{dE}{dx}$ in the lower and upper panels, respectively. The corresponding bow-tie results are shown in the right panel. The effective energy E_{eff} and response R are given by the third and fourth column in Tab. 2. The last column states the sector combinations used for the bowtie analysis. The fluxes from the EPHIN channels together with the AMS-02 measurements are displayed in Fig. 15. The black and red curves are those that use the fluxes EPHIN and AMS-02. The upper and lower curves give the time profiles for 500 MeV and 670 MeV, respectively. From the upper figure, we conclude that there is a decent agreement between the measurements. In order to quantify the deviations the lower left and right panel of Fig. 15 displays the flux measured by EPHIN and the relative difference $\frac{F_{EPHIN} - F_{AMS}}{F_{AMS}}$ as function of the flux measured by AMS-02, respectively. Marked by the blue line in the left and right panel are periods when both fluxes are the same and the difference is zero, respectively. Thus values above and below the lines indicate periods when the Flux measured by EPHIN is larger than the one measured by AMS-02 and vice versa.

From the lower right figure we conclude that the EPHIN derived fluxes agree with the one from AMS-02 within 30%. This corresponds well to the systematic uncertainty of 20% given by Kühl et al. (2016).

Figure 14: Left panels: Computed response function for $0.45 \leq \frac{dE}{dx} \leq 0.52$ and $0.52 \leq \frac{dE}{dx} \leq 0.64$ are shown in the upper and lower panel for the central segments, respectively. In order to determine the effective energy E_{eff} the bow-tie method (see Gieseler et al. (2024); Deliverable 6.1) has been applied utilizing the FFS with modulation potential ϕ between $200 \leq \phi \leq 600$ MV.

Figure 15: Upper panel: Daily averaged flux F variation of EPHIN (black curve) and AMS-02 (red curve) in the energy ranges described in 2. Note that the second channels have been scaled by a factor of 0.3. The lower panel displays on the left and right the flux measured by EPHIN and the relative difference $\frac{F_{\text{EPHIN}} - F_{\text{AMS}}}{F_{\text{AMS}}}$ as function of the flux measured by AMS-02, respectively. Marked by the blue line in the left and right panel is when both fluxes are the same and the difference is zero, respectively.

4 Conclusions

Calibrating energetic particle instruments like the [EPHIN](#) aboard [SOHO](#) is a crucial process to ensure the accuracy and reliability of measurements in space missions and particle physics experiments. [EPHIN](#) measures particles, protons, electrons, and helium across a wide range of energies from MeV to several hundred of MeV. The calibration process establishes the relationship between the instrument's raw data (e.g., counts) and the physical properties of the detected particles (e.g., energy, flux, charge, and mass).

In this report, that constitutes **deliverable 3.1**, we describe the method for derive the fluxes of protons between 50 MeV and above 600 MeV utilizing a detailed GEometry ANd Tracking ([GEANT](#)) simulation and a careful analysis using the Bow-Tie method. The fluxes were compared to different instruments, showing that our method can reproduce the fluxes from Alpha Magnet Spectrometer ([AMS](#))-02 within 20% and the helium fluxes from Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics ([PAMELA](#)).

Concerning Solar Energetic Particles ([SEPs](#)) events our new method reproduces the results from [Kühl et al. \(2015, 2017\)](#).

Thus, we conclude that [EPHIN](#)'s accuracy is comparable to other instrumentation within 20 to 30%.

Bibliography

- Adriani, O., Barbarino, G. C., Bazilevska, G. A., et al. 2016a, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 818
- Adriani, O., Barbarino, G. C., Bazilevska, G. A., et al. 2016b, *ApJ*, 818, 68
- Agostinelli, S., Allison, J., Amako, K., et al. 2003, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A*, 506, 250
- Aguilar, M., Ali Cavasonza, L., Alpat, B., et al. 2018, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 121, 051101
- Aguilar, M., Alpat, B., Ambrosi, G., et al. 2024, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 132, 261001
- Aguilar, M., Cavasonza, L. A., Ambrosi, G., et al. 2023, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 130, 161001
- Aguilar, M., Cavasonza, L. A., Ambrosi, G., et al. 2021, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 127, 271102
- Caprotti, A. S., Brüdern, M., Burmeister, S., Heber, B., & Herbst, K. 2021, *Space Weather*, 19, e02510
- Dresing, N., Yli-Laurila, A., Valkila, S., et al. 2024, *A&A*, 687, A72
- Gieseler, J., Dumbovic, M., Vainio, R., & Papaioannou, A. 2024, Deliverable 6.1: SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Gieseler, J., Heber, B., & Herbst, K. 2017, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 122, 10,964
- Herbst, K., Kopp, A., Heber, B., et al. 2010, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 115, D00I20
- Herbst, K., Muscheler, R., & Heber, B. 2017, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 122, 23
- Kühl, P., Banjac, S., Dresing, N., et al. 2015, *A&A*, 576, A120
- Kühl, P., Dresing, N., Heber, B., & Klassen, A. 2017, *Sol. Phys.*, 292, 10
- Kühl, P., Gómez-Herrero, R., & Heber, B. 2016, *Sol. Phys.*, 291, 965
- Kühl, P. & Heber, B. 2019, *Space Weather*, 17, 84
- Köberle, M., Heber, B., Kühl, P., et al. 2024, Deliverable 2.1: Report and delivery of the GEANT-4 models of SOHO/ERNE, SOHO/EPHIN, Chandra/EPHIN, Solar Orbiter/ HET and BepiColombo/SIXS, Report, SPEARHEAD Project
- Müller-Mellin, R., Kunow, H., Fleißner, V., et al. 1995, *Sol. Phys.*, 162, 483
- Rodríguez-Pacheco, J., Wimmer-Schweingruber, R. F., Mason, G. M., et al. 2020, *A&A*, 642, A7
- Sierks, H. 1997, PhD thesis, Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Fakultät, Universität Kiel
- Sullivan, J. D. 1971, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, 95, 5
- Terasa, C., Labrenz, J., Kühl, P., et al. 2013, in *International Cosmic Ray Conference*, Vol. 33, International Cosmic Ray Conference, 3627
- Usoskin, I. G., Alanko-Huotari, K., Kovaltsov, G. A., & Mursula, K. 2005, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics)*, 110, A12108
- Vainio, R., Palmroos, C., Oleynik, P., et al. 2024, Deliverable 5.1: Catalog of >100 MeV proton events, Report, SPEARHEAD Project